

CONCENTRATED NITRIC PHOSPHORIC FERTILIZER FROM PHOSPHATE CENTRAL KYZYLKUM.

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Annotation: This paper presents the results of laboratory studies, the nitrogen phosphorus fertilizers - MAP and DAP on the basis of evaporated phosphoric acid from phosphate Central Kyzylkum. We show that the products are formulated 50,31 – 52,49% P₂O₅ and 11,35 - 13,49% N and 4,36 – 50,02% P₂O₅ and 17,55 - 18,01% N, respectively, for mono-and diammonium phosphate.

Keywords: phosphoric acid, Central Kyzylkum, ammophos, fertilizer, monoammonium phosphate (MAP), diammonium phosphate (DAP), area, ammonization, component, nitroammophos.

Introduction. Ammophos - this is a two-component fertilizer containing nitrogen in the ammonium form (cation NH₄⁺) and (phosphorus in the form of anion-PO₄³⁻). They are a one-or di-substituted ammonium phosphates or mixtures thereof. Depending on the type of processed phosphate rock orthophosphates contain varying amounts of impurities (compounds of iron, aluminum, calcium, magnesium, fluorine, silicon, etc.) [1]. In fertilizers, commonly called ammophos or MAF (foreign literature MAP), the main component is monoammonium phosphate, usually in combination with 2-20% of diammonium phosphate. In Russia and in Uzbekistan

ammophos made in granular form and used as a fertilizer or as a separate component of the dry mixed fertilizers abroad - both granular and powdered in (microgranul) forms, in which case it is used as an intermediate in the production of complex, mixed fertilizer .

In accordance with the standard in the MAP, issued on the basis of apatite concentrate, the mass fraction of digestible P₂O₅ 49-52% (depending on grade), based in Ammofos Karatausskogo phosphate rock and phosphate Central Kyzylkum respectively 41-44% and 46-47% . The nitrogen content of 10-12%.

Agriculture often require a product with a smoothed ratio between nitrogen and phosphorus than the MAP. It is known that the ammonium form of nitrogen is the cheapest form of nitrogen fertilizer. Therefore, in some cases preferable issue diamphos (DAF, foreign literature DAP), the main component of which is mixed with diammonium phosphate 10-30% monoammonium phosphate. DAP is only available in granular form, use it, as well as granular IAF, as a self-phosphono nitrogen fertilizer and as an integral part of the dry bulk blends, and in several foreign countries last direction of its use is essential. In accordance with the specifications of DAP Fertilizer contains 47-48% P₂O₅ and not less than 18% nitrogen.

Ammonium phosphates are an integral part of many types of complex fertilizers, in particular such as nitroammophos, NPK, nitrodiammofos, karboammofos and karboammofoska.

In [2] the technology for production of mono- and diammonium phosphate by the method of two-stage neutralization EPA ordinary Karatau phosphorite flour. First author conducted obessulfachivanie phosphoric acid, then it ammoniated to a pH of 4-4,5. Separation ammofosnoy pulp into liquid and solid phases was carried out by centrifugation. According to the technological scheme ammofos sludge (solid phase) is directed to mixing with ammofos pulp or self pelletized and sold as magnesium ammonium phosphate. Centrate, representing a purified fosfornoammiachny solution is the feedstock for MAP and diamphos grade "A".

A method for producing purified solution of ammonium phosphate for the phased ammoniation phosphoric acid from Kingisepp phosphorite. [3] EPA initially neutralized with ammonia to a pH of 3,0-3,1 at 800° C. In the precipitate was isolated ammonium salts of iron and aluminum and a small amount of magnesium kremneftorida. Precipitation at the indicated pH values well filtered by vacuum filter. The purified filtrate obesftorivali sodium carbonate. Next, the pulp enters the second stage of neutralization with ammonia to pH 6,0-6,5. The filtered solution is almost pure ammonium phosphate fed to the evaporation stage. In [4] describes the process of obtaining ammonium phosphate based apatite EPA evaporated to 52-54% P₂O₅. Initially, it was diluted with water up to absorption 44-48% P₂O₅. Neutralization process phosphoric acid was carried out in the reactor working volume of 50 liters at a pressure above atmospheric pressure (2,5-3 atm.) to pH 4,9-5,4. Pulp temperature under these conditions rose to 125-1300C, the moisture was 24-28%. Ammophos obtained has the following composition. (Wt%): P₂O₅ usv.53,0; P₂O₅wot. 51,0; N 11,5; H₂O 1,0. To obtain concentrated brands ammophos authors of [5] propose to use clarified weak and evaporated hemihydrate EPA of Khibiny apatite concentrate with SO₃ 1,5-1,8 and 2-

2,2%, respectively. In this case, the brand received ammophos 12:55 and 12:57, with satisfactory physical and mechanical properties. Issues of production of ammonium phosphate with concentrated phosphoric acid were investigated in [6,7]. A method is proposed, which provides for the reduction of concentration of phosphoric acid to neutralize the 35-40 and 42% P₂O₅. Formed in this pulp has a moisture content of 25-27% (the temperature of the pulp 1200C), which contributes to higher yield of marketable fractions during granulation.

Accordingly, certain scientific and practical interest is a concentrated nitric phosphate fertilizers - MAP and DAP by EPA evaporated from phosphate Central Kyzylkum.

Experimental part. For laboratory experiments was used EPA production of JSC "Ammophos - Max", the composition (wt%): 19,80 P₂O₅, CaO, 0,31; 0,44 MgO; 1,41 SO₃; 1,96 Fe₂O₃ and 0,58 Al₂O₃. Uparki process of a product to a given EPA conducted P₂O₅ content at atmospheric pressure in a tubular quartz reactor equipped with a paddle stirrer. Heating of the reactor was carried out through the wall with a special oven. EPAs were obtained evaporated following concentrations 34,75; 39,60; 45,00 and 50,09% P₂O₅. To distinguish different types of phosphate, sulfate, and other insoluble compounds evaporated acid samples stored for days. Clarified part of phosphoric acid was separated from the precipitate by decantation. Concentrations of clarified phosphoric acid had values, respectively: 35,61; 40,42; 46,65 and 52,76% P₂O₅. Neutralization of phosphoric acid with ammonia evaporated conducted to pH 4,5; 4,8 and 5,1 at 80-900C.

Results. EPA evaporated with concentration 35,61% P₂O₅ after ammoniation not lose strength, its moisture content is 37-38%.

EPA with the concentration of 40,42% P₂O₅ after ammoniation humidity was 33-34%, had a good flow only at temperatures above 500C. The addition of water to the ammoniated phosphate slurry at a weight ratio of EPA: H₂O = 100:5, helped acquire a good yield with humidity 36-37%, even at 40-500C.

After ammoniation EPA with concentration 46,65% P₂O₅ at these pH values were fixed pulp. When the humidity of the pulp was 20-22%. In order to get to the starting fluid slurry of phosphoric acid is added to water at a weight ratio of EPA: H₂O = 100:24. In this case, moisture ammoniated phosphate slurry was 37-38%.

EPA with the concentration of 52,76% P₂O₅ in ammoniation at pH 3-3,5 becomes thick. Humidity pulp was 18,5-19,7%. If you add water to the EPA at a ratio of EPA: H₂O = 100:30 get moving pulp with 36-38% humidity. Ammoniated slurry was dried in an oven at 100-1050C. The composition of fertilizer analyzed for nutrients according to well-known methods [8]. These experiments are shown in Table 1.

These tables show that, depending on the pH of ammoniated phosphate concentration of the starting pulps and EPA content of P₂O₅ and N varies from 50,01-52,82 and 10,78-14,45%, respectively. A relative abundance R₂O₅usv. by citric acid, those on Trilon B and R₂O₅wot. ranged from 92,48 to 98,90 from 90,02 to 94,17 and from 80,10 to 82,68%, respectively.

Upon receipt of DAP samples evaporated EPA diluted to 35-40% P₂O₅ and ammoniated to pH 5,5; 6,0; 6,5; 7,0; 7.5 and 8,0. In this case, received phosphate slurry had a well-fluid state. Composition of the samples obtained DAP is shown in table 2. Table 2 shows that the content of P₂O₅ and N in the nitrogen phosphorus fertilizers (DAP) as a function of pH and concentration of the initial EPA is respectively 47,36-51,84 and 13,09-18,01%. The relative content of digestible form by citric acid, those on trilon B and water-soluble forms of P₂O₅ respectively 95,35-99,83; 90,88-97,26 and 80,05-84,25%.

According to the requirements of GOST, MAP and DAP contain respectively 52 and 48 % P₂O₅, 12 and 18% N, static strength should be at least 3 MPa.

The proposed method, we monoammonium phosphate containing 50,31 – 52,49% P₂O₅ and 11,35 - 13,49% N. DAP contains 47,36 – 50,02% P₂O₅ and 17,55 - 18,01% N.

Table-1

The chemical composition of nitrogen phosphorus fertilizer (monoammonium phosphate) obtained ammoniation evaporated phosphoric acid

Importance pH in ammonisation	10% of pH solution	The chemical composition of the dried product,%								P_2O_5	P_2O_5	P_2O_5
		P ₂ O ₅ common	solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in lemon acid	Solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in trB	Water- soluble of P ₂ O ₅	Ca O	Mg O	SO ₃	N _{common}	P_2O_5 , in lemon acid , %	P_2O_5 , in trB, %	P_2O_5 , %
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
On the basis of the EPA clarified 34.75% P ₂ O ₅												
4,5	4,6	52,82	52,2 4	49,74	43,6 7	0,1 9	1,1 8	2,9 2	10,7 8	98,9 0	94,1 7	82,6 8
4,8	5,0	52,49	51,7 8	49,41	42,7 7	0,1 8	1,1 6	2,7 7	11,3 5	98,6 5	94,1 4	81,4 8
5,1	5,3	52,04	50,0 2	48,86	41,8 0	0,1 7	1,1 4	2,5 2	11,8 6	96,1 2	93,8 8	80,3 2
On the basis of the EPA clarified 39,6 % P ₂ O ₅												
4,5	4,9	52,01	50,7 4	48,79	42,7 7	0,1 8	1,1 9	3,6 8	11,4 2	97,5 6	93,8 1	82,2 3
4,8	5,2	51,44	49,9 3	47,54	42,1 2	0,1 7	1,1 7	3,2 4	12,6 3	97,0 6	92,4 2	81,8 8
5,1	5,6	51,10	48,8 5	47,08	41,2 1	0,1 6	1,1 5	3,0 9	13,0 6	95,6 0	92,1 3	80,6 4
On the basis of the EPA clarified 45,00 % P ₂ O ₅												
4,5	5,0	50,99	49,5 6	47,61	41,8 2	0,1 6	1,2 1	4,2 9	12,0 1	97,1 9	93,3 7	82,0 2
4,8	5,6	50,61	48,7 5	46,68	41,2 2	0,1 5	1,1 9	4,1 2	13,0 9	96,3 2	92,2 3	81,4 5

5,1	5,7	50,28	47,9 8	46,19	40,5 0	0,1 3	1,1 6	3,9 7	14,1 2	95,4 3	91,8 7	80,5 5
On the basis of the EPA clarified 50,09 % P ₂ O ₅												
4,5	5,0	50,67	47,9 7	46,26	41,1 1	0,1 2	1,4 5	4,7 5	12,8 2	94,6 7	91,2 9	81,1 3
4,8	5,2	50,31	47,0 7	45,36	40,6 1	0,1 1	1,4 3	4,3 9	13,4 9	93,5 6	90,1 6	80,7 2
5,1	5,4	50,01	46,2 5	45,02	40,0 6	0,1 0	1,4 2	4,0 1	14,4 5	92,4 8	90,0 2	80,1 0

Table-2

The chemical composition of nitrogen phosphate fertilizer (DAP) received ammoniation evaporated phosphoric acid

Importance pH in ammonisation	10% of pH solution	The chemical composition of the dried product,%								P_2O_5	P_2O_5	$P_2O_5_{\text{вот}}$
		P_2O_5 common	solubility of P_2O_5 in lemon acid	Solubility of P_2O_5 in trB	Water- soluble of P_2O_5	Ca O	Mg O	SO_3	N common	P_2O_5 , in lemon acid , %	P_2O_5 , in trB, %	P_2O_5 , % <i>вот</i>
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
On the basis of the EPA clarified 34,75 % P ₂ O ₅												
5,5	6,5	51,84	50,5 4	47,57	41,7 5	0,1 8	1,0 9	2,2 3	13,0 9	97,4 9	91,7 7	80,5 4
6,0	6,8	51,61	50,5 5	47,84	41,7 1	0,1 8	1,0 6	2,1 4	15,2 7	97,9 5	92,7 0	82,8 2
6,5	6,9	50,94	49,9 9	47,29	41,2 8	0,1 7	1,0 5	2,0 2	15,4 4	98,1 4	92,8 4	81,0 4
7,0	7,1	50,62	49,9 4	47,21	41,5 4	0,1 6	1,0 2	1,8 9	15,8 6	98,6 6	93,2 6	82,0 7
7,5	7,3	50,30	49,9 9	47,88	41,3 4	0,1 5	1,0 1	1,5 1	16,0 6	99,3 8	95,1 9	82,1 9
8,0	7,5	50,02	49,8 4	48,09	41,5 7	0,1 5	0,9 9	1,3 7	17,5 5	99,6 4	96,1 4	83,1 1
On the basis of the EPA clarified 39,6 % P ₂ O ₅												
5,5	6,1	50,87	49,0 5	46,23	40,7 2	0,1 7	1,1 9	3,6 9	13,8 6	96,4 2	90,8 8	80,0 5
6,0	6,6	50,64	49,4 1	46,71	40,5 8	0,1 6	1,1 7	3,4 6	15,4 9	97,5 7	92,2 4	80,1 3
6,5	6,7	50,48	49,8 9	47,48	40,7 2	0,1 5	1,1 4	3,1 5	15,7 6	98,8 3	94,0 6	80,6 7
7,0	7,1	50,23	49,8 5	47,34	40,6 0	0,1 4	1,1 2	2,9 7	15,9 5	99,2 5	94,2 5	80,8 3

7,5	7,4	50,13	49,9 5	47,53	40,9 7	0,1 3	1,0 9	2,7 6	16,1 9	99,6 4	94,8 1	81,7 3
8,0	7,6	49,89	49,7 6	47,35	41,0 1	0,1 2	1,0 7	2,5 1	17,7 6	99,7 4	94,9 1	82,2 0

table continued

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13
On the basis of the EPA clarified 45,00 % P ₂ O ₅												
5,5	6,4	50,05	48,94	47,34	40,62	0,096	1,26	4,78	15,27	97,78	94,58	81,16
6,0	6,6	49,47	48,89	46,89	40,24	0,095	1,24	4,59	15,61	98,83	94,78	81,34
6,5	7,0	49,28	48,76	47,50	40,28	0,094	1,21	4,34	16,02	98,94	96,39	81,74
7,0	7,2	48,97	48,50	47,26	40,17	0,089	1,17	3,99	16,43	99,04	96,51	82,03
7,5	7,3	48,71	48,27	47,04	40,96	0,085	1,15	3,57	17,24	99,10	96,57	84,09
8,0	7,4	48,25	48,17	46,93	40,65	0,079	1,13	3,02	17,89	99,83	97,26	84,25
On the basis of the EPA clarified 50,09 % P ₂ O ₅												
5,5	6,5	49,73	47,42	45,76	40,90	0,091	1,40	5,64	15,68	95,35	92,01	82,24
6,0	6,7	49,46	47,54	45,66	40,76	0,088	1,39	5,36	15,94	96,12	92,32	82,41
6,5	6,9	49,39	47,56	46,01	40,83	0,085	1,25	4,81	16,31	96,29	93,16	82,67
7,0	7,2	49,01	47,23	45,99	40,82	0,079	1,19	4,52	16,77	96,37	93,84	83,29
7,5	7,4	48,81	47,65	45,83	40,80	0,077	1,16	3,93	17,37	97,62	93,89	83,59
8,0	7,6	47,36	46,75	44,67	39,79	0,065	1,15	3,17	18,01	98,71	94,32	84,02

Table-1

The chemical composition of nitrogen phosphorus fertilizer (monoammonium phosphate) obtained ammonation evaporated phosphoric acid

Importance pH in ammonisation	10% of pH solution	The chemical composition of the dried product, %								
		P ₂ O ₅ common	solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in lemon acid	Solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in trB	Water- soluble of P ₂ O ₅	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	N _{common}	
On the basis of the EPA clarified 34,75 % P ₂ O ₅										
4,5	4,6	52,82	52,24	49,74	43,67	0,19	1,18	2,92	10,78	
4,8	5,0	52,49	51,78	49,41	42,77	0,18	1,16	2,77	11,35	
5,1	5,3	52,04	50,02	48,86	41,80	0,17	1,14	2,52	11,86	
On the basis of the EPA clarified 39,6 % P ₂ O ₅										
4,5	4,9	52,01	50,74	48,79	42,77	0,18	1,19	3,68	11,42	
4,8	5,2	51,44	49,93	47,54	42,12	0,17	1,17	3,24	12,63	
5,1	5,6	51,10	48,85	47,08	41,21	0,16	1,15	3,09	13,06	
On the basis of the EPA clarified 45,00 % P ₂ O ₅										
4,5	5,0	50,99	49,56	47,61	41,82	0,16	1,21	4,29	12,01	
4,8	5,6	50,61	48,75	46,68	41,22	0,15	1,19	4,12	13,09	
5,1	5,7	50,28	47,98	46,19	40,50	0,13	1,16	3,97	14,12	

On the basis of the EPA clarified 50,09 % P ₂ O ₅									
4,5	5,0	50,67	47,97	46,26	41,11	0,12	1,45	4,75	12,82
4,8	5,2	50,31	47,07	45,36	40,61	0,11	1,43	4,39	13,49
5,1	5,4	50,01	46,25	45,02	40,06	0,10	1,42	4,01	14,45

Table-2

The chemical composition of nitrogen phosphorus fertilizer (diammonium phosphate) obtained ammoniation evaporated phosphoric acid

Importance pH in ammonisation	10% of pH solution	The chemical composition of the dried product,%							
		P ₂ O ₅ common	solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in lemon acid	Solubility of P ₂ O ₅ in trB	Water- soluble of P ₂ O ₅	CaO	MgO	SO ₃	N _{common}
On the basis of the EPA clarified 34,75 %P ₂ O ₅									
5,5	6,5	51,84	50,54	47,57	41,75	0,18	1,09	2,23	13,09
6,0	6,8	51,61	50,55	47,84	41,71	0,18	1,06	2,14	15,27
6,5	6,9	50,94	49,99	47,29	41,28	0,17	1,05	2,02	15,44
7,0	7,1	50,62	49,94	47,21	41,54	0,16	1,02	1,89	15,86
7,5	7,3	50,30	49,99	47,88	41,34	0,15	1,01	1,51	16,06
8,0	7,5	50,02	49,84	48,09	41,57	0,15	0,99	1,37	17,55
On the basis of the EPA clarified 39,6 %P ₂ O ₅									
5,5	6,1	50,87	49,05	46,23	40,72	0,17	1,19	3,69	13,86
6,0	6,6	50,64	49,41	46,71	40,58	0,16	1,17	3,46	15,49
6,5	6,7	50,48	49,89	47,48	40,72	0,15	1,14	3,15	15,76
7,0	7,1	50,23	49,85	47,34	40,60	0,14	1,12	2,97	15,95
7,5	7,4	50,13	49,95	47,53	40,97	0,13	1,09	2,76	16,19
8,0	7,6	49,89	49,76	47,35	41,01	0,12	1,07	2,51	17,76
On the basis of the EPA clarified 45,00 %P ₂ O ₅									
5,5	6,4	50,05	48,94	47,34	40,62	0,096	1,26	4,78	15,27
6,0	6,6	49,47	48,89	46,89	40,24	0,095	1,24	4,59	15,61
6,5	7,0	49,28	48,76	47,50	40,28	0,094	1,21	4,34	16,02
7,0	7,2	48,97	48,50	47,26	40,17	0,089	1,17	3,99	16,43
7,5	7,3	48,71	48,27	47,04	40,96	0,085	1,15	3,57	17,24
8,0	7,4	48,25	48,17	46,93	40,65	0,079	1,13	3,02	17,89
On the basis of the EPA clarified 50,09 %P ₂ O ₅									
5,5	6,5	49,73	47,42	45,76	40,90	0,091	1,40	5,64	15,68
6,0	6,7	49,46	47,54	45,66	40,76	0,088	1,39	5,36	15,94
6,5	6,9	49,39	47,56	46,01	40,83	0,085	1,25	4,81	16,31
7,0	7,2	49,01	47,23	45,99	40,82	0,079	1,19	4,52	16,77
7,5	7,4	48,81	47,65	45,83	40,80	0,077	1,16	3,93	17,37
8,0	7,6	47,36	46,75	44,67	39,79	0,065	1,15	3,17	18,01

From the results of studies show that not all products comply with the requirements represented IAF and DAF. This is, apparently, due to a high content of iron and free sulfuric acid in the original EPA, which are formed when ammoniation ironammoniyne phosphate and ammonium sulfate and diluting the final product, reducing its content in P₂O₅ and N.

Conclusion. Thus, on the basis of the results of laboratory tests can be concluded that by ammoniation evaporated phosphoric acid from phosphate Central Kyzylykum is possible to obtain highly concentrated nitric phosphate fertilizers, which are very similar in composition to the MAP and DAP.

To increase the concentration of P₂O₅ and N in compound fertilizers is necessary before starting evaporation extractivity EPA or partially ammoniated phosphate with the release of iron and aluminum. This process is the subject of our further research.

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